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Contents

Preface to International Journal of Frontier Sciences.....	2
High Seropositivity of HIV, Hepatitis and Syphilis in Prisoner Blood Donors than the General Population Volunteers from the Punjab, Pakistan –A Longitudinal 13 Years Study	2
Vascular Reactivity during Cardiopulmonary Bypass in Patients at Punjab Institute of Cardiology & Shalamar Hospital Lahore, Pakistan	12
Prevalence of Common Infectious Diseases in Paediatric Age Group Admitted in Children’s Hospital Lahore, Pakistan.....	19
Effect of the addition of the antioxidant taurine on the complete blood count of whole blood stored at room temperature and at 4°C for up to 3 days	29
Life Quality of Obstructive Sleep Apnoea patients after Non-Invasive Positive Pressure Ventilation Therapy	44

Preface to International Journal of Frontier Sciences

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Hundreds of thousands of research papers are published every year all over the world. Scientists give their best in the field of research. Every researcher has a valuable contribution to scientific knowledge and ultimate betterment of human being in different aspects of life. Every researcher is important for science and human being in terms of his/her contribution to research. Researchers put their brain, energy, time and resources they have.

Researchers give their best to research and their contribution should be acknowledged. If researcher's contribution is not delivered to the relevant individuals, it is useless for researcher as well as for the community. Every research needs proper platform for its recognition. Research is being recognized through conferences, seminars and publications. There are multiple platforms for this purpose.

We, the team of **The International Journal of Frontier Sciences** have started an effort to give our contribution for recognition and dissemination of researchers' effort to everyone. It is a platform for a quality research work, accessible to every scientist around the globe.